

Natural antiseptics: Study of the antimicrobial potential of the genus *Chaenomeles* introduced species

Khromykh Nina, Didur Oleh, Sklyar Tetyana

Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Dnipro, Ukraine)

In the face of the relentless growth of pathogenic microorganisms' resistance to traditional antibiotics, the search for alternative antimicrobial compounds among the plant world is a strategic task of modern pharmacy and biology. Plants of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. have long been known as a powerful source of biologically active substances of various chemical classes.

The accumulation and composition of beneficial phytochemicals vary, which is a key factor in assessing their resource potential. The biosynthesis pathways of secondary metabolites significantly depend on the environmental factors. Since the genus *Chaenomeles* species originate from remote geographical regions (China, Japan), it is extremely important to investigate whether they retain their antimicrobial properties when grown in the specific climatic conditions of the steppe zone of Ukraine. Studying the collection of the Botanical Garden of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University allows us to assess the introduced plants adaptive capacity and identify the most promising taxa for the creation of herbal medicines, which will contribute to biodiversity rational use.

The aim of the study was to determine the antimicrobial potential of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. plants, introduced into the steppe zone.

The study objects were the genus *Chaenomeles* species and hybrids: *Ch. japonica*, *Ch. speciosa*, and *Ch. × superba*.

The antibacterial and antifungal activity of isopropanol fruit extracts was determined by disc-diffusion method. The well-known antibiotics ofloxacin (for bacterial strains) and itraconazole (for fungal strain) were used as positive controls.

All studied *Chaenomele* fruit extracts demonstrated significant level of the pathogenic organism's growth inhibition (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of *Chaenomeles* fruit extracts on bacterial growth: 1 – *Ch. japonica* (200 µg/mL), 2 – *Ch. speciosa* (200 µg/mL), 3 – *Ch. × superba* (200 µg/mL), 4 – *Ch. japonica* (50 µg/mL), 5 – *Ch. speciosa* (50 µg/mL), 6 – *Ch. × superba* (50 µg/mL), 7 – ofloxacin (5 µg/disc)

All studied fruit extracts had a dose-dependent inhibitory effect against both Gram-positive (*M. lysodeikticus*, *S. epidermidis* ATTC149) and Gram-negative (*E. dissolvens*, *P. aeruginosa*) pathogenic bacteria.

The antibacterial effects of all fruit extracts at a concentration of 200 µg/mL were comparable to the ofloxacin effect at a dose of 5 µg/disc, and also had significant antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* fungus (Table 1).

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of fruit extracts (concentration 200 µg/mL) of the *Chaenomeles* introduced plants ($x \pm SD$, $n = 5$)

Test culture	Inhibition zone diameter (mm) along with disc diameter (6 mm)			
	<i>Ch. japonica</i>	<i>Ch. speciosa</i>	<i>Ch. × superba</i>	Ofloxacin
<i>Erwinia dissolvens</i> B170	11.67 ± 0.31 ^a	18.01 ± 0.26 ^b	16.73 ± 0.49 ^b	30.17 ± 0.55 ^c
<i>Escherichia coli</i> B906	18.47 ± 1.45 ^a	15.57 ± 0.35 ^b	17.03 ± 0.42 ^a	30.13 ± 0.65 ^c
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> B907	13.17 ± 0.15 ^a	9.53 ± 0.25 ^b	17.67 ± 0.15 ^c	21.4 ± 0.44 ^d
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> B920	14.90 ± 0.36 ^a	16.20 ± 0.30 ^b	16.13 ± 0.31 ^b	27.9 ± 0.44 ^c
<i>Micrococcus lysodeikticus</i> 2665	15.30 ± 0.10 ^a	14.70 ± 0.20 ^b	21.53 ± 0.40 ^c	19.27 ± 0.25 ^d
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> B904	17.02 ± 0.17 ^a	16.87 ± 0.15 ^a	12.47 ± 0.15 ^b	26.63 ± 0.31 ^c
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> B209	13.60 ± 0.17 ^a	18.87 ± 0.15 ^b	14.30 ± 0.60 ^a	25.03 ± 0.51 ^c
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> ATCC149	15.93 ± 0.25 ^a	19.03 ± 0.12 ^b	17.67 ± 0.21 ^c	23.63 ± 0.12 ^d
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> B919	13.77 ± 0.31 ^a	29.60 ± 0.17 ^b	33.33 ± 0.15 ^c	32.20 ± 0.56 ^c
<i>Candida albicans</i>	15.10 ± 0.20 ^a	18.43 ± 0.15 ^b	19.93 ± 0.06 ^c	Itraconazole 12.3 ± 0.2 ^d

Note: Different letters in a row indicate statistically significant differences in the means of the pair being compared (according to Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

The established significant inhibitory effect of fruit extracts confirmed the manifestation of high antibacterial and antifungal potential of the genus *Chaenomeles* introduced plants in a new environmental condition.

The species specificity of the fruit extracts antimicrobial activity against various pathogenic strains characterizes all the *Chaenomeles* studied plants as promising sources for the development of new powerful natural antiseptics with a broad spectrum of action.